

STUDIES IN THE FLUORESCENCE OF DYESTUFFS.

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The fluorescence and extinction coefficients of a number of dyestuffs in alcoholic solutions have been studied.

The König Marten spectrophotometer, which has been used in measuring absorption and fluorescence, admits of an easy separation of sodium lines $5890\text{\AA}/5896\text{\AA}$. It has been found that absorption capacity per molecule increases with dilution up to a certain limit after which Beer's law is obeyed. The absorption in ultraviolet has also been studied.

For the determination of maximum fluorescence yield of dyestuffs and for its variation with concentrations, three different absolute photometric methods have been followed by observing the fluorescence light (a) opposite to, (b) in the same as, and (c) normal to the direction of exciting light. The maximum fluorescence yield for fluorescein at $365\ \mu\mu$, is about 0.72. The experimental results confirm the general observation that the fluorescence yields remain constant up to a limiting concentration, beyond which the yields fall off with increase in concentrations. Wawilow's method of determining fluorescence yields by comparing the relative intensities at a particular wave-length at different concentrations of a particular dyestuff gave some time, incorrect results and the absolute photometric method has been advocated for accurate results.

The influence of wave-lengths of exciting light on the fluorescence yields, has been studied and the yields have been found to be roughly proportional to the wave-lengths of exciting light.

The molecular conductivities of some of the purified dyestuffs in aqueous alcohol have been determined. The molecular conductivities when plotted against square root of concentration, do not give linear relationship even at $0.01M$ as is to be expected from Debye-Hückels' theory.

The various mechanisms for quenching of fluorescence have been discussed and the whole experimental results tend to support the view that in solution the dyestuffs form micelle ions which break up on dilution.

The ratio of fluorescent energy to the absorbed energy for producing fluorescence has been variously designated as fluorescence yield or fluorescing power or specific capacity for fluorescence. Wood and Dunoyer ("La structure de la Matière", 1921, p. 307) have shown that for resonance radiation in vapours of sodium and mercury, the fluorescence yield is unity. In the case of many dyestuffs in solution Wawilow (*Z. Physik*, 1924, 22, 266) found the ratio to be much less than unity.

Szczeniowski (*Bull. Int. Acad. Polonaise*, 1927, A, 127) studied the aqueous solution of sodium fluoresceinate with the aid of a photoelectric cell and found this ratio to be 0.71.

The solution of dyestuffs may be excited to emit fluorescence by light of all wave-lengths shorter than the wave-lengths of fluorescence band (Stoke). The determination of relation between the specific exciting power, *i.e.*, the fluorescence excited per unit of absorbed radiation and the wave-lengths of exciting light is a problem of considerable interest.

Einstein postulated on the basis of quantum theory that the velocity of photochemical reaction should be inversely proportional to frequency of exciting light. If fluorescence be produced by absorption in quanta, the fluorescence yield should depend on the wave-lengths of the exciting light. Nichols and Merrit (*Phys. Rev.*, 1910, 31, 381) noted a decrease in energy efficiencies of eosin and resorufin at shorter wave-lengths and this decrease appeared to be of the same order of magnitude as one would expect to find if a uniform quantum efficiency existed. Wawilow (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 43, 307; *Z. Physik*, 1927, 42, 311) found that in case of fluorescein, the fluorescent yield showed a definite proportionality of energy efficiencies with the wave-lengths in the region $4047\text{\AA} - 2537\text{\AA}$, indicating a uniform quantum efficiency. In recent years Lewschin (*J. Chem. Phys. Russ.*, 1931, 2, 641), Harrison and Leighton (*Phys. Rev.*, 1931, 36, 899) and Fabrikant (*Phys. Zeit. Sowjet Union*, 1933, vi, 3, 567) showed that the efficiency is proportional to wave-lengths of exciting light under suitable conditions of experiments.

Walter (*Wied. Ann.*, 1888, 34, 22) observed that the specific capacity for fluorescence of solutions of fluorescein remained constant with the increase in concentrations up to a certain limit and then rapidly fell off. This critical concentration according to Walter is 3×10^{-4} g. per c.c., but according to Lepine (*Ann. phys.*, 1915, 4, 207) and Mackleubergh and Valentiner (*Z. Physik*, 1914, 18, 267) is of the order of 10^{-5} g. per c.c. According to Perrin (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 178, 1978) the fluorescing power of solutions of dyestuffs decreases exponentially with increase in concentration and is given by following equation,

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 e^{-kc}$$

where Φ is the fluorescing power at concentration c and Φ_0 is the maximum fluorescing power at zero concentration.

Wawilow (*Z. Physik*, 1925, 31, 750), however, found that his extensive experimental results could best be correlated by a modified equation of the form,

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 e^{-(kc - c_0)}$$

Bouchard (*J. chim. phys.*, 1936, **33**, 50) has recently drawn the conclusion that the intensity of fluorescent light at concentrations, where the fluorescing power remains constant, is so feeble that the rigorous testing of Perrin's or Wawilow's equation is not possible.

The quenching of fluorescence with increase in concentrations has been variously explained by

(a) process of resonant induction (F. Perrin, *Ann. phys.*, 1929, **12**, 169; 1932, **17**, 283; *Compt. rend.*, 1924, **178**, 1978, 2252; J. Perrin, *Compt. rend.*, 1923, **177**, 469, 612, 665; 1927, **184**, 1097);

(b) deactivating collision of second kind (Wawilow, *Z. Physik*, 1925, **31**, 750);

(c) formation of complex micelles (Lewschin, *Z. Physik*, 1927, **43**, 237; Banow, *ibid.*, 1929, **58**, 811);

(d) change in electrolytic dissociation (Sherill, Desha, and Harrison, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1493; Eisenbrand, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **144A**, 441; Bouchard (*loc. cit.*).

The absorption spectra of fluorescent dyes in solution have been studied in recent years by Banow (*Z. Physik*, 1929, **58**, 811; 1930, **64**, 121). Speas (*Phys. Rev.*, 1928, **31**, 569), and Lewschin (*loc. cit.*). Banow has shown that the changes in absorption bands with increase in concentrations are similar in nature to those observed during the process of adsorption of dyestuffs on colloidal particles. Lewschin found that change in absorption spectra was marked at a concentration where quenching of fluorescence begins.

The subject of the molecular conductivity and transport number of ions in solutions of electrolytes which can give rise to micelles, is now engaging considerable interest (Robinson and Moillet, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **A143**, 630; Lottermoser and Puschell, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, **53**, 175; Hartley, Collie and Samis, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, **32** 795). Many dyes fall within this class and Robinson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 245), has recently shown that methylene blue, which has been upto now regarded as a dyestuff and which forms a true solution, gives a maximum in the value of molecular conductivity with increase in concentrations indicating the formation of ionic micelles.

In this investigation, we have studied simultaneously the fluorescing power under different conditions of excitation, the absorption spectra and the molecular conductivity of certain dyes in alcoholic solution and the changes that are observed in these magnitudes as the concentration of the solution increases and an attempt has been made to correlate these properties in the interpretation of our experimental results.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The dyestuffs were very carefully purified before use. The salting out process of Robinson(*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A131**, 576, 596) was not found to be satisfactory. Dyestuffs were purified by crystallisation from suitable solvents. Fluorescein was purified by repeated crystallisation from acetic acid; eosin, rhodamine B from acetone; acriflavine, benzoflavine, rhodulin orange and rhodamine 6 G from aqueous alcohol; magdala red, phosphine 2 G and phloxine from alcohol. The concentrations have been expressed in gram molecules per litre, the molecular formulæ being as given in Colour Index (edited by F. M. Rowe, 1st Ed.).

1. Fluorescein	... $C_{20}H_{10}O_5Na_2$	6. Rhodamine B	... $C_{20}H_{21}N_2O_3Cl$.
2. Eosin	... $C_{20}H_6O_5Br_4Na_2$.	7. Acriflavine	... $C_{14}H_{14}N_2Cl$.
3. Rhodamine 6 G	... $C_{25}H_{27}N_2O_3Cl$.	8. Benzoflavine	... $C_{21}H_{20}N_2Cl$.
4. Rhodulin orange	... $C_{17}H_{20}N_3Cl$.	9. Phloxine.	... $C_{20}H_4O_5Cl_3Br_4K_2$.
5. Magdala red	... $C_{10}H_{20}N_3Cl$.	10. Phosphine 2 G	... $C_{20}H_{18}N_2NO_2$.

Absolute alcohol was used throughout in making solution of these dyes. For measurements of conductivity, aqueous alcohol of specific conductance of 3×10^{-7} reciprocal ohms at 29°5 was used to have reproducible and accurate readings.

Absorption Spectra.

The absorption spectra as well as fluorescent intensities in the visible region were measured by a König-Marten spectrophotometer which was specially constructed for the purpose by Schmidt and Haensch. It contained a prism of very high dispersion, enabling an easy separation of the sodium lines 5820Å and 5896Å. The wave-lengths were calibrated on a drum by the rotation of which any monochromatic radiation could be separated. The molar extinction coefficients ϵ were calculated from the equation

$$\epsilon = \frac{\log_{10} \tan \theta_1 - \log_{10} \tan \theta_2}{c \cdot d}$$

where d is the thickness of the cell in centimeters, and θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles for equal illumination with solutions and pure solvents respectively. Rectangular cells made of plane parallel glass plates with a stopper at the top, were used and their thickness varied between 0.025 to 10 cm. in order to avoid errors arising from possible failures of Beer's law,

For the measurements of extinction coefficients in the ultraviolet, the Adam Hilger outfit with a sector photometer and a quartz spectrograph was used. These results were further verified by the measurements of absorption with a sensitive Moll thermopile and galvanometer system. A parallel beam of rays from a point source quartz-mercury lamp was allowed to fall on a cell containing dye solution through a combination of filters, Schott and Gen UG2, 1 mm. thick and BG 4, 2 mm. thick, which allow only $365 \mu\mu$ to pass. The incident and transmitted radiations were measured with Moll thermopile and galvanometer. The extinction coefficients, ϵ , were calculated from the equation

$$I_{\text{transmitted}} = I_{\text{incident}} \cdot 10^{-\epsilon \cdot d}$$

Quantitative Methods of Measurements of Fluorescence Yields by Absolute Photometric Methods.

Three methods have been followed in this investigation for the quantitative measurements of fluorescence yields of dyestuffs.

Method A.—For observation of fluorescence in concentrated solutions ($M/1000$ and above) and for noting the effect of different thicknesses of cell on critical concentrations beyond which the fluorescence yield diminishes, the spectral photometric method, as usually adopted by Wawilow (*Z. Physik*, 1924, 22, 266; 1925, 31, 750), was followed. In this method the fluorescent light was observed opposite to the direction of incidence of exciting light. The exciting light was a point-source quartz-mercury lamp, placed in a metallic jacket with a window opposite to point source. This light was made parallel by use of a quartz lens, placed suitably in a metallic jacket. The parallel beam of light was allowed to fall upon the surface of the cell containing dye solution, through an ultraviolet filter (Schott and Gen U G 2, 1 mm. thick) and of 1 cm. thick cell containing very dilute solution of copper sulphate. The rectangular cells containing the fluorescent solution or the filtering solution were made of plane parallel plates of fused quartz with a stopper at the top. The mercury-quartz lamp was placed on one side of the König-Martens spectrophotometer and the angle at which the light fell upon the surface never exceeded 20° . The quartz-mercury lamp was run at a constant current of 2 amperes, fed from a storage battery of 30 volts. The fluorescent light was compared with the light from a tungsten lamp. The comparison tungsten lamp was enclosed in a tubular metallic jacket and light from this source entered one of the slits of König-Martens spectrophotometer through a right angled prism, while the fluorescent light entered the other

FIG. 1.

slit. The intensity of light from the tungsten lamp could be varied at will by placing milk glasses in front of the lamp. The tungsten lamp was run from a storage battery of 4 volts and its energy of radiation at various wavelengths was calibrated with the aid of a standard lamp supplied by Kipp and Zonen. The whole experimental arrangement can better be understood from the diagram (Fig. 1A).

With this mode of excitation, the fluorescence yields can be calculated as follows:

Let us suppose for sake of simplicity, that the exciting light is falling in the direction of AB and the emitted light is observed along the reverse direction CD, then the contribution to the intensity of fluorescent light in a solid angle $d\omega$ from any volume $ds \cdot dx$ round a point P within the cell will be

$$dF_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = KCI_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 ds e^{-k \cdot c \cdot x} dx \cdot e^{-k'cx} \frac{dw}{4\pi}$$

where $I_{\lambda} d\lambda$ is the energy of incident light expressed in ergs/cm.²/sec.

$a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ is the fraction of the absorbed energy transformed into fluorescent energy in the spectral region λ_1 and $\lambda_1 + d\lambda_1$.

K is the molar extinction coefficient of solution for exciting light (wavelength λ);

K' , the molar extinction coefficient of solution for fluorescent light (wavelength λ_1);

C , the molar concentration of dyestuff solution and,

ds is the effective area which fills up the solid angle opening dw of the slit.

On integrating, the above equation within the limit 0 and τ , the thickness of the cell, we shall get the total fluorescent light $F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$, emerging from the cell in a solid angle dw from the surface ds .

$$\begin{aligned} F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 &= I_{\lambda} d\lambda ds \cdot \frac{dw}{4\pi} \cdot K \cdot C \cdot a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \int_0^{\tau} e^{-(k+k')c \cdot l} \cdot dx \\ &= I_{\lambda} d\lambda ds \cdot \frac{dw}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{KC}{(k+k')C} \left[1 - e^{-(k+k')c \cdot l} \right] a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \cdot \tau \end{aligned}$$

now, $dw = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{R^2}$, where $\Delta\sigma$ is the area of the slit opening and R is the

distance of the cell to the slit, *i.e.*

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda}{4\pi} \cdot \Delta\sigma \frac{ds}{R^2} \cdot \frac{K}{(k+k')} \left[1 - e^{-(k+k')c \cdot l} \right] a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \cdot \tau$$

If the arrangement is such that the fluorescent light fills completely the aperture of the spectrophotometer, the total surface of the cell from which the fluorescent radiation is received may be regarded as $= A \cdot R^2 / f^2$, where A/f^2 is the effective aperture of the instrument (A , the area and f , the focal

length of the lens), taking this into account, the expression becomes

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda}{4\pi} \cdot \Delta\sigma \frac{A}{f^2} \cdot \frac{K}{k+k'} \left[1 - e^{-(k+k')cl} \right] a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$$

thus the intensity observed will be independent of the distance of the fluorescent cell.

We made some preliminary experiments to test this and found that the intensity of fluorescent light remains practically independent of the distance of the cell from the slit provided that the portion illuminated, may fill up the effective aperture.

Now the fluorescent light $F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ was compared with the radiation from a comparison lamp $I_{0\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ coming from a uniform source transmitted through milk glasses. This light (standardised by Kipp and Zonen band lamp) entered the same slit (divided into two by a diaphragm) having the same slit area and filled up by the same solid angle A/f^2 .

The effective intensity of radiation from the comparison lamp between wave-lengths λ_1 and $\lambda_1 + d\lambda_1$ at the slit would be

$$I_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = I_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \cdot \Delta\sigma \cdot \frac{A}{f^2}$$

Now, we compare the intensities of these two radiations by means of the same spectrophotometer by rotating the nicol and finding out the angles for equal illumination; in this case we have,

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda = I_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \frac{I}{\tan^2 \theta}$$

where θ is the angle for equal illumination, taking the zero reading to be at 45° . Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1'}{I_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1} &= \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda}{I_{0\lambda_1} d\lambda_1} \cdot \frac{K}{4\pi(k+k')} \left[1 - e^{-(k+k')cl} \right] a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 \\ &= \frac{I}{\tan^2 \theta} \quad \text{or} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{I}{\tan^2 \theta} = I_{\lambda} d\lambda \frac{K}{4\pi(k+k')} \left[1 - e^{-(k+k') c.l} \right] \frac{a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{I_{0\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}.$$

In this equation, the values of all the terms are known and hence the value of $a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ can be calculated for each wave-length of the fluorescence spectrum at each concentration of dyestuffs. These values are plotted in the graph and the integrated area would be equal to $I_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$. The value of $I_{\lambda} d\lambda$, the total incident light in ergs/cm.²/sec. is known, the corresponding value of 'a' for each concentration is, thus, known.

Method B.—This method of observing fluorescent light in the direction of incident exciting light is very convenient for the study of the fluorescence in dilute solution ($M/1000$ and below). The experimental arrangement was very simple and may easily be understood from the diagram (Fig. 1B). A quartz lens system of 2.5 cm. focal length was used to have a strong beam of parallel rays from the point source quartz-mercury lamp. The filtering device for obtaining monochromatic radiation and the arrangement for the comparison of intensities of light are the same as in method A.

Since there are few corrections which are to be made when the exciting source is monochromatic, extensive measurements of fluorescence were made with the ultraviolet radiation ($365\mu\mu$) from mercury-quartz lamp as the source of excitation. This mode of excitation has the advantage that scattered light from the cell would not affect our results and our data will be more dependable than those of the previous investigators in this field.

With this method, the calculation of fluorescence yield was made as follows:—

The intensity of fluorescent light at any point in the cell of thickness l , will be

$$dF_{\lambda_1} = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot e^{-kx} K \cdot dx e^{-k'(l-x)}$$

Other factors, which ultimately vanish and do not come into consideration, are not put here for the sake of simplicity of mathematical expression. The symbols have the usual significance as described in Method A.

Total fluorescent light emerging from the cell will be

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_\lambda d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot K \cdot e^{-kl} \int_0^l e^{-(k-k')x} \cdot dx$$

$$= \frac{I_\lambda d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{K}{k-k'} \cdot e^{-k'l} \left[1 - e^{-(k-k')l} \right]$$

The factor $\frac{F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 4\pi'(k-k')}{K \cdot e^{-k'l} [1 - e^{-(k-k')l}]}$ can easily be calculated for each wavelength of fluorescent light. By plotting these values for each concentration, we should get the integrated area as equivalent to $I_\lambda d\lambda a$ for that concentration. $I_\lambda d\lambda$ being known, 'a' for each concentration can easily be calculated.

Method C.—The above two methods are not suitable for the study of the effect of the wave-lengths of exciting light on fluorescence yields of dyestuffs, because the scattered rays from visible exciting source would affect our results. For the study of the effect of wave-lengths of exciting light the following method of observing fluorescent light normal to the direction of exciting light was adopted. (Fig. 1c).

With this mode of excitation, the fluorescent light $F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$, would be

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_\lambda d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{k}{k'} \cdot e^{-ks} \left[1 - e^{-k'd} \right]$$

where d is the thickness of the cell, S , the distance of the surface layer of the solution to the layer along whole of which the fluorescent light is falling on the slit of the spectrophotometer. Other symbols have the usual significance (Method A).

For higher values of $k'd$ (at shorter wave-length)

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_\lambda d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{K}{k'} \cdot e^{-ks}$$

and for smaller values of $k'd$ (*i.e.* at longer wave-lengths)

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1}{4\pi} \cdot K.d. e^{-ks}.$$

In these equations, all factors are known, 'a' can be calculated as mentioned before.

With this mode of excitation, a small amount of scattered and diffusely reflected light was unavoidable, the correction to be applied on this account was determined by making measurements throughout the spectrum, when the cell was filled up with solvent alone, everything else remaining same.

Isolation of Monochromatic Light for Excitation.

Most of the investigators employed a monochromator to study the influence of each wave-length on the intensity of fluorescent light. The exciting light when passed through a monochromator is of so feeble intensity that accurate study of the problem is not possible. Moreover, the selection of wave-lengths at short intervals, is of little value because the variation would be so small that it may be counted as experimental errors. In view of all these difficulties, we have employed in the present investigation, the following suitable monochromatic filters to isolate the mercury lines.

313 $\mu\mu$ —Chance Bros. U. V. filters 1 mm. thick + 1 cm. of 5% CuSO_4 solution + 1 cm. 0.02% $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution.

365 $\mu\mu$ —Schot and Gen filter U. G. 2, 1 mm. thick + B.G. 4, 2 mm. thick.

404 $\mu\mu$ —Wratten violet filter + 1 cm. of 2% CuSO_4 solution.

436 $\mu\mu$ —Zeiss monochromatic filter C + 1 cm. of 1% CuSO_4 solution.

546 $\mu\mu$ —Zeiss monochromatic filter B + 1 cm. of 5% CuSO_4 solution.

577 $\mu\mu$ } —Zeiss monochromatic filter A + 1 cm. of 5% CuSO_4 solution.
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Calibration of Comparison Lamp.

The band lamp No. 205, used in this investigation, has been calibrated at Physical Laboratory of the University of Utrecht, Holland. The calibration method was described by L. S. Ornstein, D. Vermulen, and E.F.M. V.d Held (*J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, 1930, 20, 573). The use of this lamp in

spectroscopic work has been described by Orstein, Moll and Burger in their book " Objektive spectral Photometrie " (Vieweg, Braunschweig).

The absolute energy in ergs per Ångstrom per sec. per unit solid angle at wave-length 6000Å at different current intensity is given in a tabular form. The certificate of calibration supplies the colour temperature of the band lamp as a function of current intensity through the lamp. A table containing the values of E_λ / E_{ms} as a function of λT , where T is colour temperature, was also supplied. True temperature corresponding to colour temperature is found out from a table. Thus the relative distribution of energy for other wave-lengths can be calculated and in doing so, a slight correction due to spectral emissivity of tungsten at different wave-lengths is also considered.

*Measurements of Molecular Conductivities of Dyestuffs
in Alcoholic Solution.*

All the measurements were done in dilute solutions, where correction due to the conductivity of alcohol has a great significance.

All the measurements were made in a water thermostat at the temperature specified in each case. The temperature was kept accurate and constant within $\pm 0.005^\circ$ by use of an electric thermo-regulator.

Apparatus.—The conductivities were measured with the help of an alternating current galvanometer of Wattmeter type devised by H. Mukherjee (*Z. Physik*, 1930, 64, 286). The galvanometer gave accurate and reproducible readings at 30-50 milliamperes. The sensitiveness of the galvanometer was about 2×10^{-7} amperes, when the current in the fixed coil was 50 milliampere. The experimental errors did not exceed 0.1%, even when the highest resistance was measured. The resistance boxes were all non-inductively wound variable resistances from 0.1 to 10,000 ohms. The current was supplied from a double contact tuning fork oscillator which was found to give equally intense positive and negative current by means of a oscillograph. The current from the oscillator was made to pass through a variable resistance box, by the adjustment of which, current intensities could be changed. The arrangement for measurements will be clear from the diagram (Fig. 2). Before working, it is necessary that galvanometer should remain in electrically symmetrical position between the fixed coils. This was assured by passing a current of 50 milliamperes through the fixed coils and short circuiting the moving coils and adjusting the position of the latter when there was no current. A tapping key was placed in the battery circuit so that no current was passing through the solution except in time of taking readings.

FIG. 2.

Two types of cells made of Jena glass used in covering the range of conductivity from 500×10^{-11} to 1×10^{-11} reciprocal ohms are shown in the diagram (Fig. 2).

The cell 'A', which was used for solutions of relatively high conductivities, had a cell constant 0.148, a capacity of 80 c. c. and rectangular smooth platinum electrodes. The cell B had a cell constant 0.04517, a capacity of 80 c. c. was used in measuring low conductivities. The electrodes were stout and smooth sheet of platinum whose relative positions were fixed by sealing with glass. Smooth platinum was used as the dycstuffs were found to be adsorbed on black or grey platinum and reproducible readings could not be obtained. Readings were taken at two different frequencies of oscillator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Absorption Spectra of Alcoholic Solutions of Dyestuffs.

In the following pages the molecular extinction coefficients of dyestuffs in two or three concentrations are given graphically against the wave-lengths expressed in $\mu\mu$ (Figs. 3, 4, 5, 6).

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

We have observed in all cases excepting for rhodamine B and phosphine-2 G that the molecular absorption coefficients increase with dilution up to a certain limit after which Beer's law is obeyed. This means that the ratio of the number of molecules with greater absorbing power to the total number of molecules increases with decrease in concentration of dyestuffs. This may be possible if molecular aggregation takes place at concentrated solutions and aggregates have less absorbing power than the molecules from which they are formed; dilution, favouring the breaking up of micelles, increases the relative number of simple molecules. We have not observed any change in absorption curves with increase of concentrations as Söderborg (*Ann. Physik*, 1913, 41, 381), and Van der Plaats (*ibid.*, 1915, 47, 429) observed in case of aqueous solution. This we may explain, by assuming that in alcoholic solution a slight aggregation takes place with increase of concentration, but in aqueous solution the dye molecules suffer considerable aggregations with increase of concentrations. This has been confirmed by

FIG. 5.

FIG. 6.

FIG. 7.
Acridflavine.FIG. 8.
Acridflavine.FIG. 9.
Rhodamine 6 G.FIG. 10.
Rhodamine 6 G.

Söderborg (*loc. cit.*) and Banow (*Z. Physik*, 1929, **88**, 811), who have shown that a rapid extinction of fluorescence with a considerable and a relatively slow extinction of fluorescence with a slight alteration of absorption spectra. This has also been further confirmed by Mlle Vitte (*J. chim. phys.*, 1926, **23**, 276), Bouchard (*ibid.*, 1936, **33**, 127), who observed that decrease o-

fluorescing power of dyestuffs with concentrations is less rapid in alcoholic solution than in aqueous solution.

Such results in absorption coefficients may also be expected if we assume that absorption bands are due to ions of definite type. There would not be any appreciable shift of band as the number of ions is varied but the absorption coefficients may vary (Nichols and Merrit, *Phys. Rev.*, 1904, 19, 18; 1910, 31, 376).

It may be added here that our results in absorption in ultraviolet may be useful in the sense that recently Grisebach (*Z. Physik*, 1936, 101, 13) tried to establish a relation between absorption curves with polarisation curves specially as to the cause of negative polarisation.

The molar-extinction coefficients obtained by both the methods at 365 $\mu\mu$ gave almost concordant results, as will be evident from Table I.

TABLE I.

Dyestuffs.	Mol. extinct. coeff. at 365 $\mu\mu$ by		Dyestuffs.	Mol. extinct. coeff. at 365 $\mu\mu$ by	
	Thermoelectric method.	Photographic method.		Thermoelectric method.	Photographic method.
Fluorescein	2000	2100	Magdala red	7800	7400
Eosin	1200	1200	Benzoflavine	1100	1200
Rhodamine 6 G	3600	4000	Acriflavine	2000	2000
Rhodulin orange	600	600	Phosphine 2G	2300	2500
Rhodamine B	550	625	Phloxine	1200	1200

Influence of Thickness of Cell on Fluorescence Yields.

TABLE II (vide Fig. 7).

Acriflavine.

Cell—5 mm. thick. Method of excitation—A. $I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 16$ ergs/cm.²/sec.
Wave-lengths. $I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ for concentrations of

	M/1000.	M/2000.	M/4000.	M/8000.	M/16,000
480 $\mu\mu$	0.0044	0.005	0.006	0.0065	0.007
490	0.0063	0.0077	0.009	0.0115	0.012
500	0.007	0.009	0.01	0.0115	0.012
510	0.0072	0.0085	0.009	0.01	0.01
520	0.006	0.0065	0.007	0.0074	0.0074
530	0.005	0.0055	0.0058	0.0058	0.0058
540	0.004	0.0045	0.0045	0.0045	0.0045
550	0.003	0.0035	0.0035	0.0035	0.0035
560	0.002	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025
570	0.0012	0.0017	0.0017	0.0017	0.0017

$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 16$ erg cm.²/sec.

C. no.	...	M/1000	M/2000	M/4000	M/8000	M/16000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda$	...	4.2	5.06	5.6	6.1	6.4
δ	...	0.26	0.316	0.35	0.38	0.40

TABLE III (*vide* Fig. 8)*Acriflavine.*

Cell—20 mm. thick.

Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of				
	M/1000.	M/2500.	M/5000.	M/10,000.	M/20,000.
480 $\mu\mu$	0.004	0.0047	0.005	0.055	0.0062
490	0.006	0.0065	0.0076	0.01	0.01
500	0.007	0.0076	0.01	0.012	0.012
510	0.0072	0.0080	0.009	0.01	0.01
520	0.006	0.0065	0.007	0.0078	0.0078
530	0.005	0.0055	0.0057	0.0061	0.0061
540	0.004	0.0045	0.005	0.0055	0.0055
550	0.0025	0.003	0.0035	0.0038	0.0038
560	0.0020	0.0022	0.0025	0.0028	0.0028
570	0.0012	0.0015	0.0018	0.002	0.0020

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 16 \text{ ergs/cm}^2 \text{./sec.}$$

Conc.	...	M/1000	M/2500	M/5000	M/10,000	M/20,000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	4.20	4.45	5.62	6.30	6.5
a	...	0.26	0.28	0.35	0.394	0.405

TABLE IV (*vide* Fig. 9).*Rhodamine 6 G.*

Cell—5 mm. thick.

Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of				
	M/1500.	M/3000.	M/6000.	M/12,000.	M/24,000
540 $\mu\mu$	0.01	0.012	0.016	0.02	0.025
550	0.015	0.02	0.033	0.045	0.05
560	0.016	0.023	0.033	0.04	0.042
570	0.016	0.021	0.025	0.03	0.03
580	0.013	0.016	0.0197	0.021	0.02
590	0.01	0.0125	0.0158	0.0155	0.0155
600	0.0064	0.008	0.01	0.01	0.01
610	0.004	0.006	0.0075	0.008	0.008

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 25 \text{ ergs./cm}^2 \text{./sec.}$$

Conc.	...	M/1500	M/3000	M/6000	M/12,000	M/24,000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	8.8	12.05	15.65	18.25	19.25
a	...	0.352	0.48	0.626	0.73	0.77

TABLE V (vide Fig. 10).

Rhodamine 6 G.

Cell—20 mm. thick.

Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of				
	M/1500.	M/6000.	M/12,000.	M/24,000.	M/48,000.
540 $\mu\mu$	0.01	0.015	0.02	0.03	0.03
550	0.0125	0.0288	0.043	0.05	0.05
560	0.015	0.028	0.037	0.042	0.042
570	0.0155	0.02	0.025	0.03	0.03
580	0.015	0.018	0.02	0.022	0.022
590	0.01	0.012	0.015	0.017	0.017
600	0.006	0.01	0.012	0.015	0.015
610	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.012	0.012

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 25 \text{ ergs./cm}^2\text{./sec.}$$

Conc.	...	M/1500	M/6000	M/12000	M/24000	M/48000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	8.05	13.05	17.05	19.5	19.5
a	...	0.32	0.52	0.70	0.78	0.78

It will appear from the above experimental results that if readings be taken on the red end of the fluorescence spectrum as Wawilow (*loc. cit.*) did, the critical concentrations obtained will be different for different thicknesses of the cell as will be evident from the following summarised data.

Concentration at which $I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ remains constant

Cell thickness.	Acriflavine.	Rhodamine 6 G.
20 mm.	M/10,000	M/24,000
5	M/2000	M/6000

FIG. 11.

Fluorescein.

FIG. 12.

Eosin.

Such results may be explained from the previous mathematical deduction (Method A) in which we have shown

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 k}{4\pi(k-k')} \cdot \left[1 - e^{-(k+k')c.l} \right]$$

On expanding and neglecting the value of k and k' , which are evidently small in dilute solution at red end of the spectrum, we get

$$F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 = \frac{I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1 k.c.l}{4\pi}$$

That is, the fluorescent intensity ($F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$) will be proportional to concentration of dyestuffs and thickness of cell. Therefore, in dilute solution, for similar values of $F_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ with increase of thickness of cell, a proportionate decrease of concentration of dyestuffs is expected, if all the experimental conditions satisfy the ideal condition, i.e., if k and k' are small and absorption coefficient follows Lambert's law.

It is, therefore, clear that Wawilow's method of studying the fluorescing power by taking the fluorescent intensity readings at red end of the fluorescence spectrum may enable us only to gain knowledge about the law of variation of fluorescing power with concentrations; but not about the values of critical concentrations of dyestuffs for which purpose, we are to calculate the whole of the fluorescence energy emerging from a solution by making necessary absorption corrections.

FIG. 13.

Rhodamine 6 G.

FIG. 14.

Rhodamine orange.

Influence of the Thickness of Cell on Fluorescence Yields.

It is worth while determining carefully if fluorescence yields of dyestuffs solution for the same concentrations vary with the thickness of the cell. In the following table, the values of 'a' (the yields) for each concentration at different thicknesses of cell are given. The values are obtained from graphical interpolation (when required) of the experimental data recorded in previous tables.

TABLE VI.

Acriflavine.

Thickness of cell.	Values of 'a' at concentrations of			
	<i>M</i> /1000.	<i>M</i> /2000.	<i>M</i> /4000.	<i>M</i> /8000.
5 mm.	0.26	0.31	0.35	0.38
20 mm.	0.26	0.28	0.33	0.385

Rhodamine 6 G.

	<i>M</i> /1500.	<i>M</i> /3000.	<i>M</i> /6000.	<i>M</i> /12,000.	<i>M</i> /24,000
	5 mm.	0.35	0.48	0.62	0.73
20 mm.	0.32	—	0.52 (7)	0.70	0.78

Thus it appears from the above data that fluorescence yields at same concentration of dyestuffs are of the same value, whatever be the thickness of the cell. It is, therefore, clear that if fluorescence yields are calculated from entire fluorescent band by making necessary absorption corrections, the yields are independent of cell thickness.

FIG. 15.

Benzoflavine.

FIG. 16.

Magdala red.

FIG. 17.

Rhodamine B.

FIG. 18.

*Phosphine 2 G.**Influence of Concentration of Solution on Fluorescence Yields.*

It was sometime difficult to obtain the energy distribution in the entire fluorescence spectrum, as for example, in dilute solution, the fluorescent intensity on the red end of the spectrum was very feeble and accurate readings were not possible; similarly in concentrated solutions, readings on the short wave side were not accurate due to high absorption. These values were extrapolated from graph. Photometric method allows an experimental error of $\pm 3\%$. Hence the error in calculating the yields by this method of graphical extrapolation would be of the same order.

TABLE VII (vide Fig 11).

Fluorescein.

$$p_H = 12.0. \quad I_\lambda d\lambda_1 = 130 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

Wave-lengths.	$I_\lambda d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of					
	M/500.	M/1250.	M/2500.	M/5000.	M/10000.	M/20000
510 $\mu\mu$	0.0255	0.038	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.081
520	0.035	0.0584	0.094	0.11	0.14	0.15
530	0.0425	0.0758	0.12	0.15	0.17	0.18
540	0.053	0.081	0.106	0.12	0.14	0.16
550	0.05	0.0707	0.094	0.096	0.11	0.11
560	0.0416	0.062	0.084	0.090	0.0955	0.097
570	0.035	0.0486	0.065	0.07	0.076	0.070
580	0.0204	0.0406	0.05	0.056	0.06	0.06
590	...	0.028	0.038	0.044	0.045	0.045
600	...	0.020	0.03	0.038	0.038	0.038
Conc. ...	M/500	M/1250	M/2500	M/5000	M/10,000	M/20,000
$I_\lambda d\lambda a$...	31.4	49.0	70.2	77.4	88.0	92.8
a ...	0.24	0.38	0.54	0.60	0.68	0.71

TABLE VIII (vide Fig. 12).

Eosin.

$$p_H = 12.0. \quad I_\lambda d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

Wave-lengths.	$I_\lambda d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of					
	M/500.	M/1000.	M/2000.	M/5000.	M/10,000.	M/20,000.
530 $\mu\mu$	...	...	...	0.05	0.089	0.104
540	0.0135	0.03	0.046	0.115	0.218	0.22
550	0.02	0.053	0.10	0.215	0.26	0.28
560	0.04	0.075	0.143	0.206	0.24	0.24
570	0.056	0.10	0.122	0.18	0.18	0.18
580	0.0517	0.083	0.117	0.155	0.155	0.155
590	0.047	0.073	0.10	0.145	0.145	0.145
600	0.047	0.067	0.09	0.12	0.120	0.120
610	0.0338	0.03	...	...	...	...
Conc ...	M/500	M/1000	M/2000	M/5000	M/10,000	M/20,000
$I_\lambda d\lambda a$...	30.0	49.3	76.6	116.0	133.8	136
a ...	0.15	0.246	0.383	0.58	0.669	0.68

Remark—A subsidiary maximum at about wave-length 590-600 $\mu\mu$ is observed along with the principal maximum at 570 $\mu\mu$ at concentrated solutions. This maximum is shifted towards the violet end along with the principal maximum with dilution.

TABLE IX (vide Fig 13).

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 300 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

Rhodamine 6G
 $I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of

Wave lengths.	M/750.	M/1500.	M/3000.	M/7500.	M/15,000.	M/30,000
540 μ	...	0'10	0'125	0'175	0'225	0'225
550	0'0306	0'125	0'22	0'40	0'50	0'50
560	0'06	0'15	0'24	0'37	0'43	0'45
570	0'0933	0'155	0'29	0'27	0'32	0'32
580	0'103	0'145	0'16	0'22	0'22	0'22
590	0'09	0'125	0'14	0'17	0'17	0'17
600	0'08	0'105	0'125	0'15	0'15	0'15
610	0'063	0'09	0'11	0'13	0'13	0'13
620	0'05	0'075	0'085	0'09	0'09	0'09
Conc. ...	M/750	M/1500	M/3000	M/7500	M/15,000	M/30 000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$...	62'0	104'2	132'5	187	219	219
a ...	0'207	0'347	0'44	0'623	0'73.	0'73

TABLE X (vide Fig. 14).

Rhodulin orange.

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

 $I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of

Wave-lengths.	M/400	M/800.	M/2000.	M/4000.	M/8000.	M/16,000.
510 μ	...	0'0417	0'069	0'126	0'165	0'187
520	0'03	0'063	0'187	0'204	0'20	0'24
530	0'053	0'093	0'176	0'254	0'26	0'26
540	0'074	0'115	0'15	0'210	0'218	0'218
550	0'0736	0'081	0'142	0'17	0'167	0'17
560	0'053	0'072	0'10	0'143	0'142	0'145
570	0'044	0'0537	0'097	0'123	0'12	0'12
580	0'0417	0'0513	0'0714	0'10	0'10	0'10
590	0'0354	0'0478	0'057	0'066	0'066	0'066
600	0'0268	0'04	...	...	...	...
Conc. ..	M/400	M/800	M/2000	M/4000	M/8000	M/16000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$...	40'72	62'02	96'31	128'0	135'0	136'0
a ...	0'2036	0'31	0'48	0'64	0'675	0'68

Remark—A slight trace of maximum is observed at about 580 μ at very concentrated solutions along with the principal maximum at 545 μ .

TABLE XI (*vide* Fig. 15).*Benzoflavine.*

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of					
	<i>M</i> /625.	<i>M</i> /1250.	<i>M</i> /2500	<i>M</i> /5000.	<i>M</i> /10,000.	<i>M</i> /20,000.
490 $\mu\mu$	...	0.024	0.0316	0.055	0.088	0.158
500	0.0096	0.064	0.11	0.155	0.21	0.21
510	0.046	0.10	0.14	0.21	0.20	0.20
520	0.08	0.103	0.15	0.186	0.175	0.175
530	0.06	0.10	0.13	0.158	0.162	0.162
540	0.045	0.087	0.107	0.126	0.126	0.126
550	0.043	0.056	0.09	0.114	0.114	0.114
560	0.044	0.056	0.071	0.10	0.10	0.10
570	0.043	0.0446	0.077 (?)	0.092	0.092	0.092
580	0.033	0.04	0.08 (?)	0.0867	0.0867	0.0867
Conc.	... <i>M</i> /625	<i>M</i> /1250	<i>M</i> /2500	<i>M</i> /5000	<i>M</i> /10,000	<i>M</i> /20,000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	... 39.1	69.2	90.3	123.3	128.1	128.0
<i>a</i>	... 0.196	0.346	0.45	0.616	0.64	0.64

Remark—A subsidiary maximum is observed at about 560-570 $\mu\mu$ along with the principal maximum 520-525 $\mu\mu$ at concentrated solutions.

TABLE XII (*vide* Fig. 16).*Magdala red.*

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of					
	<i>M</i> /1200.	<i>M</i> /3000.	<i>M</i> /6000.	<i>M</i> /12,000.	<i>M</i> /24,000.	<i>M</i> /48,000.
560	...	...	...	0.02	0.024	0.028
570	...	...	0.04	0.073	0.11	0.128
580	...	0.05	0.078	0.112	0.161	0.166
590	0.035	0.072	0.087	0.138	0.172	0.171
600	0.072	0.078	0.09	0.122	0.121	0.128
610	0.052	0.066	0.076	0.10	0.10	0.10
620	0.05	0.056	0.076	0.09	0.092	0.092
630	0.056	0.06	0.076	0.08	0.08	0.08
640	0.051	0.056	...	...	...	...
Conc.	... <i>M</i> /1200	<i>M</i> /3000	<i>M</i> /6000	<i>M</i> /12,000	<i>M</i> /24,000	<i>M</i> /48,000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	... 29.6	41.6	54.1	68.7	79.6	82.2
<i>a</i>	... 0.148	0.208	0.27	0.343	0.398	0.411

Remark—A subsidiary maximum is observed at 630 $\mu\mu$ at a concentration *M*/1200. This maximum is shifted towards the violet end along with the principal maximum 600 $\mu\mu$ with dilution.

TABLE XIII (vide Fig. 17).

Rhodamine B.

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 220 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

 $I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of.

Wave-lengths.	M/1000.	M/2500.	M/5000.	M/10,000.
540 $\mu\mu$	...	...	0.0125	0.03
550	...	...	0.063	0.09
560	0.023	0.09	0.12	0.156
570	0.05	0.115	0.19	0.214
580	0.075	0.13	0.225	0.23
590	0.10	0.11	0.14	0.15
600	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.10
610	0.065	0.07	0.075	...
Conc. ...	M/1000	M/2500	M/5000	M/10,000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$...	34.7	70.5	100	109.
a ...	0.158	0.32	0.455	0.495

TABLE XIV (vide Fig. 18).

Phosphine G.

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm}^2/\text{sec.}$$

 $I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of

Wave-lengths.	M/1300.	M/3250.	M/6500	M/13,000
480 $\mu\mu$	...	...	0.0075	0.009
490	...	...	0.021	0.0235
500	...	0.016	0.029	0.03
510	...	0.0175	0.031	0.033
520	0.01	0.0185	0.032	0.035
530	0.0115	0.02	0.028	0.031
540	0.013	0.015	0.023	0.026
550	0.01	0.0125	0.018	0.02
560	0.0075	0.01	0.014	0.015
570	0.00575	0.0075	0.012	0.0125
580	0.0044	0.06	...	...
Conc ...	M/1300	M/3250	M/6500	M/13000
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$...	6.5	13.07	22.0	24.0
a ...	0.0325	0.065	0.11	0.12

At concentrated solutions perhaps there are two maxima between 490 to 540 $\mu\mu$ which overlap

TABLE XV (*vide* Fig. 19).*Phloxine.*

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 200 \text{ ergs/cm.}^2/\text{sec.}$$

$I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of

Wave-lengths.	M/1000.	M/5000.	M/10,000.	M/20,000	
530 $\mu\mu$	...	0.0224	0.0275	0.032	
540	...	0.06	0.074	0.087	
550	...	0.10	0.12	0.15	
560	0.005	0.075	0.10	0.14	
570	0.02	0.063	0.083	0.081	
580	0.031	0.060	0.06	0.06	
590	0.0367	0.054	0.054	0.054	
600	0.3	...	...	...	
610	0.0234	...	...	...	
Conc.	...	M/5000	M/10,000	M/20,000	
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	11.85	39.3	48.0	54.0
a	...	0.059	0.197	0.24	0.27

TABLE XVI (*vide* Fig. 20).*Acridine.*

$$I_{\lambda} d\lambda = 80 \text{ ergs/cm.}^2/\text{sec.}$$

$I_{\lambda} d\lambda_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ at concentrations of

Wave-lengths.	M/500.	M/1000.	M/2000.	M/4000.	M/8000.	M/160,000.	
480 $\mu\mu$	0.005	0.006	0.01	0.0125	0.016	0.016	
490	0.106	0.0144	0.019	0.0275	0.045	0.045	
500	0.0186	0.0234	0.031	0.0446	0.051	0.051	
510	0.022	0.0327	0.033	0.039	0.039	0.039	
520	0.025	0.0257	0.030	0.035	0.035	0.035	
530	0.0217	0.0227	0.0234	0.024	0.024	0.024	
540	0.0177	0.0170	0.017	0.018	0.019	0.019	
550	0.015	0.017	0.018	0.018	0.015	0.015	
560	0.0105	0.012	0.0125	0.0125	0.0125	0.0125	
Conc.	...	M/1000	M/2000.	M/4000	M/8000	M/16,000	
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	15.1	20.0	22.3	27.15	29.7	29.7
a	...	0.19	0.25	0.28	0.35	0.38	0.38

A subsidiary maximum at about 550 $\mu\mu$ was observed along with the main peak; at 500 $\mu\mu$.

The following values for the maximum fluorescence yields of dyestuffs in alcoholic solutions were observed, when the exciting wave-length was $365\mu\mu$.

Dyestuffs.	Maximum fluorescence yields.	Dyestuffs.	Maximum fluorescence yields.
1. Fluorescein	0.72	6. Magdala red	0.425
2. Eosin	0.68	7. Rhodamine B	0.5
3. Rhodamine 6G	0.75	8. Phosphine 2G	0.225
4. Rhodulin orange	0.68	9. Phloxine	0.28
5. Benzoflavine	0.66	10. Acriflavine	0.40

The experimental results confirm the general observation that the fluorescence yields remain constant at very low concentrations but beyond this limiting concentration, the yields fall off very rapidly with increase in concentrations.

FIG. 19.

Phloxine.

FIG. 20.

Acriflavine.

We have observed that with increase of concentrations, the maxima of the fluorescence bands are always shifted towards the red end of the spectrum.

Fluorescence Yields as a Function of Wave-lengths of Exciting Light.

TABLE XVII (vide Fig. 21).

*Rhodamine 6 G.*Conc. = $M/20,000$.

Wave-lengths of exciting light ($\mu\mu$)	...	313	365	436	546
Incident energy (ergs/ cm^2 ./sec.)	...	6	21	10	25
Wave-lengths.	$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$				
540 $\mu\mu$	0'003	0'016	0'007	0'0172	
550	0'0065	0'022	0'014	0'034	
560	0'007	0'029	0'0138	0'04	
570	0'005	0'0245	0'012	0'032	
580	0'004	0'0184	0'0085	0'025	
590	0'003	0'0162	0'007	0'0188	
600	0'002	0'012	0'005	0'014	
610	0'0015	0'008	0'004	0'0108	
620	...	0'006	...	0'008	
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	4'0	14'4	8'1	21'4
a	...	0'66	0'70	0'81	0'86

All the values of $I_{\lambda} d\lambda a_{\lambda_1} d\lambda_1$ are plotted in the graph.

TABLE XVIII.

*Rhodamine B.*Conc. = $M/10,000$.

Exciting wave-lengths ($\mu\mu$)	...	313	365	546	577, 579
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda$ (ergs/ cm^2 ./sec.)	...	6'36	19'6	24'5	15'5
$I_{\lambda} d\lambda a$	...	2'8	9'8	12'9	6'2
a	...	0'44	0'50	0'53	0'40

TABLE XIX.

*Magdala red.*Concentration = $M/20,000$ Exciting wave-lengths ($\mu\mu$) $I_{\lambda} d\lambda$ (erg./cm./sec.²) $I_{\lambda} d\lambda$ a

a

375

365

546

577, 579

6

13.0

20.0

8.0

2.1

5.3

10.3

4.0

0.35

0.40

0.52

0.50

FIG. 21.

Rhodamine 6 G.

FIG. 22(a).

FIG. 22(b)_a
Magdala red.

It would be evident from the above experimental facts that the structure of fluorescence band does not materially alter with change of wave-length of exciting light.

Though our results (Fig. 22) are not very exhaustive and only limited to a few wave-lengths, we may safely deduce the conclusion that the fluorescence yields of dyestuffs are proportional to wave-lengths of exciting light up to a maximum of visible absorption band. Within the visible absorption band, the yields slightly increase or remain constant in accordance with the observation of previous investigators. The yields rapidly fall off at the approach of maximum of fluorescence band and finally become zero.

*Molecular Conductivities of some of the Fluorescent Dyestuffs
in Alcoholic Solution.*

TABLE XX (vide Fig. 23).

Rhodamine B.

Temp. = 29°.

Mol. conc. (C).	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.	Mol. conc. (C).	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.
0.002	0.0447	5.72	0.00025	0.0158	6.065
0.001	0.0316	6.005	0.000125	0.01118	6.05
0.0005	0.02236	6.11	0.0000625	0.0079	6.00

TABLE XXI (vide Fig. 24).

Eosin.

Temp. = 30°.

Mol. conc. (C).	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.	Mol. conc. (C).	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.
0.002	0.0447	40.0	0.000125	0.01118	63.26
0.001	0.0316	46.71	0.0000625	0.0079	67.0
0.0005	0.02236	52.7	0.00003125	0.0056	70.0
0.00025	0.0158	58.25			

TABLE XXII (*vide* Fig. 24).*Acriflavine.*

Temp. = 29.5°.

Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.	Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.
0.002	0.0447	36.5	0.000125	0.01118	48.3
0.001	0.0316	40.4	0.0000624	0.0079	49.7
0.0005	0.02236	43.8	0.00003125	0.00562	51.05
0.00025	0.0158	46.4			

TABLE XXIII (*vide* Fig. 25).*Magdala red.*

Temp. = 30°.

Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.	Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.
0.002174	0.04672	23.4	0.0002717	0.01648	27.4
0.001087	0.03297	24.68	0.0001359	0.01166	28.3
0.0005435	0.0233	26.3	0.00006793	0.00824	29.2

TABLE XXIV (*vide* Fig. 23).*Rhodamine 6 G.*

Temp. = 30°.

Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.	Mol. conc.	$\sqrt{C}$.	Mol. conductivity.
0.001476	0.03872	28.4	0.0000937	0.009675	33.48
0.00075	0.02737	30.26	0.00004685	0.00684	34.27
0.000375	0.01933	31.56	0.00002342	0.00483	34.87
0.0001875	0.01366	32.58			

It will appear from the graphs that when the molecular conductivities of dyestuffs in alcohol are plotted against square root of molar concentrations, they do not give a linear relation, even at a concentration of 0.001M as is expected from Debye and Hückel's theory. It has sometimes been found that the molecular conductivities pass through a maximum. The significance of this abnormal behaviour has been discussed by various investigators.

FIG. 23.

Rhodamine B.

FIG. 24.

FIG. 25.

The Mechanism of Quenching of Fluorescence.

The quenching of fluorescence of dyestuffs with increase in concentration or by addition of salts has been explained by various investigators as due to deactivating collisions of second kind.

Lewschin (*Z. Physik*, 1927, **43**, 230) found that for rhodulin orange and fluorescein in sucrose, the values of specific fluorescent capacity are practically the same as in ordinary liquids of small viscosity. From this result, Lewschin concluded that the mechanism for quenching for fluorescence must be the same in solid and in liquid solution and therefore practically independent of viscosity. Banow (*Z. Physik*, 1929, **58**, 811)

confirmed this observation and has further shown that a three hundred fold increase in viscosity scarcely affects the extinction curves. Further evidences against the deactivation collision, have been supplied by Bouchard (*loc. cit.*) who showed that the enormous effect of glycerine on the quenching coefficients is due to specific solvent effects and if due corrections are made, the effects of viscosity on the quenching coefficient is negligible (8-16%). Hence it is not unreasonable to suppose that the mechanism for quenching of fluorescence is almost the same in liquid and in viscous media. Lewschin (*loc. cit.*) studied the effect of temperature on specific fluorescent capacity in concentrated solutions. Though temperature increases the number of collisions, the fluorescence yields increases at the same time. Bouchard (*loc. cit.*) has confirmed the above observations which go against a collision of second kind as means of quenching. Banow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, 153A, 172) has further shown that increase of temperature, has, sometimes a decreasing effect on the quenching of fluorescence.

F. Perrin (*Compt. Rend.*, 1931, 192, 1727) suggested that the more rapid decrease of fluorescence with increasing concentrations and smaller optimum concentration of solutions of fluorescein, when aqueous potassium chloride solution is used as solvent in place of pure water, supports the view that the decrease of fluorescence on increasing concentrations beyond the optimum, is due to association of molecules, as conceived by Walter (*Wied. Ann.*, 1888, 34, 22; 1889 36, 518).

We have observed in our work a close parallelism between the change of molar absorption coefficients with concentrations and change of fluorescence yields. It is interesting to note that in very dilute solution, where Beer's law seems to hold, the fluorescence yields remain constant. Further increase in concentration diminishes the yields as well as absorption capacity per molecules. This leads us to think that the same causes, which diminish the yields, would also account for the deviation of Beer's law in the direction indicated by our experiments. It will be difficult to explain on purely collision hypothesis the change of absorption coefficients to the extent actually observed by us. We are, thus, inclined to look for an explanation of the observed facts in the formation of micelle ions.

In Figure 26 the values for absorption capacity ϵ_c/s_c (where ϵ_c is the molar absorption coefficient at concentration C , ϵ_o its value at infinite dilution) and fluorescent capacity a_c/a_o (where a_c is the fluorescent yield at concentration C and a_o is the fluorescent yield at infinite dilution) are plotted against $\log C$. It is interesting to note that all these straight lines meet at the same point corresponding approximately to critical concentrations. It is not unreasonable to assume that causes which are

FIG. 26.

responsible for variation of absorption capacity with concentration, may also account for the variation of fluorescence yields with concentrations.

We have observed that if molecular conductivities of fluorescent dyes be plotted against square root of molar concentrations, they give curves similar in nature to those obtained by Moillet, Collie and Robinson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 120) in the case of methylene blue, *metabenzopurpurine* and long chain paraffin salts. In view of the similarity of curves obtained, we are tempted to believe in agreement with these investigations that at concentrated solutions of dyestuffs, ionic micelles are formed and these micelles are gradually broken into simpler forms and finally into ions, as we increase the dilution.

It may be pointed out that the molecular conductivities plotted against the square root of concentrations give curves which may be divided into two parts. The tangential straight lines drawn to these curves meet at a point corresponding to a certain concentration. It is interesting to note that these concentrations or the concentrations corresponding to maxima of conductivity coincide with the concentrations after which rapid quenching of fluorescence begins. It also suggests that fluorescence is largely dependent on the state of ions,

It is premature to draw any picture of micelle formations unless we have some data on transport number of dye ions. Further investigations on the transport number of fluorescent dyes are in progress with a view to throw light on the constitution of ionic micelles which may exist in solution.

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